

Host plant range of *Pseudococcus saccharicola* Takahashi

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Mealybug *P. saccharicola* sometimes occurs on rice cultured in the greenhouse. We compared its development on 24 common ricefield plants from families Poaceae (20) and Cyperaceae (4).

Twenty-five- to 30-d-old individual host plants were maintained in 20-cm-diam clay plots. Plants were covered with 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cages with side and top nylon mesh (1 mm²) vents. Five pairs of newly emerged adults were

released per cage in a no-choice test. Host suitability was based on survivorship and nymphal stage duration of the issuing progeny. Each cage was a treatment in a randomized complete block design with 10 replications. The experiment was conducted in the greenhouse at an average temperature of 28.0 ± 1.2 °C and 66.0 ± 2.9% relative humidity.

Nymphs survived on 17 of the 24 plants tested (see table). Significantly higher survival rates occurred with rice (90.6%), *Echinochloa glabrescens* (81.2%), and *Panicum repens* (80.5%). The most progeny per female were produced on *P. repens* (39.0 nymphs) and *E. glabrescens* (38.2 nymphs). The shortest life cycles—and therefore the

most nutritious hosts—occurred on rice and *E. glabrescens* (21.0 d), followed by *Triticum aestivum* (21.5 d) and *Paspalidium flavidum* (22.2 d).

Plant hosts were ranked overall and for each life cycle parameter by taking the average of the survival, progeny, and life cycle rankings. The top-ranked hosts overall were rice > *E. glabrescens* = *P. repens* > *Leptochloa chinensis*. *Ischaemum rugosum* and *Cyperus iria* were the least acceptable hosts with the lowest nymphal survival of 9.0-11.6% and the longest life cycle of 25.2-26.0 d. Seven species—four Poaceae and three Cyperaceae—were not hosts of *P. saccharicola*. ■

Host plant range of *P. saccharicola*^a. IRRI greenhouse, Feb-May 1990.

Host	Parameter				Overall average ranking ^d		
	Nymphal survival (%) ^b		Progeny (no. crawlers/female)			Duration of life cycle (d) ^c	
Poaceae							
TN1 rice	90.6 ± 4.2	a	30.5 ± 4.5	bc	21.0 ± 0.8	a	1
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	81.2 ± 2.5	ab	38.2 ± 6.2	ab	21.0 ± 2.2	a	2
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	80.5 ± 10.8	ab	39.0 ± 10.5	a	25.0 ± 0.8	cd	2
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	70.4 ± 21.1	bc	19.0 ± 9.4	de	22.8 ± 3.9	bc	3
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L. em. Thell.	63.9 ± 18.0	b d	13.5 ± 4.4	ef	21.5 ± 0.6	a	4
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	50.4 ± 18.3	de	17.8 ± 5.6	d f	22.8 ± 2.1	bc	5
<i>Brachilaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	58.8 ± 11.2	cd	12.2 ± 3.1	ef	24.8 ± 1.5	cd	6
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i> (Retz.) A. Cameron	11.2 ± 6.0	gh	23.2 ± 9.0	cd	22.2 ± 4.8	ab	7
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	26.8 ± 18.0	fg	15.5 ± 10.2	def	25.2 ± 2.5	cde	8
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	40.2 ± 32.3	ef	13.0 ± 8.5	ef	27.2 ± 1.0	def	9
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	25.6 ± 11.1	fg	15.2 ± 5.1	def	30.0 ± 2.9	f	10
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	28.9 ± 21.1	fg	8.5 ± 4.7	f	30.8 ± 1.3	f	11
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	11.6 ± 5.1	gh	16.2 ± 3.9	d f	27.0 ± 1.6	def	12
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i> (= <i>P. distichum</i> L.)	14.0 ± 3.1	gh	19.2 ± 7.1	de	26.5 ± 1.3	def	12
<i>Brachilaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	12.1 ± 6.3	gh	12.2 ± 3.1	ef	28.8 ± 0.5	def	13
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	9.0 ± 1.6	gh	11.5 ± 2.4	ef	26.0 ± 3.4	def	13
Cyperaceae							
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	11.6 ± 9.2	gh	12.5 ± 7.0	ef	25.2 ± 2.5	c-e	13

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.01$) by LSD statistical test. No nymphs survived on *Chloris barbata* Sw., *Eriochloa procerata* (Retz.) C. E. Hubb., *Imperata cylindrica* (L.) Beauv., and *Isachne globosa* (Thund.) O. K. in the Poaceae family, or on *Cyperus brevifolius* (Rottb.) Hassk., *C. rotundus* L., and *C. kyllingia* Endl. in the Cyperaceae family.

^bNymphal survival (%) = $\frac{\text{Crawlers becoming adults (no.)}}{\text{Initial crawlers (no.)}} \times 100$. ^cn = 10. ^d1 = best, 13 = worst.